

Figure 3

b

	Group-specific AA											C-terminus consensus	
	35	53	172	178	218	234	331	341	344	370	372		394
Tub1A1	Q	N	S/A	Q	N	G	N	R	Q	L	K	D	VEGE G E G E E E V
Tub1A2	Q/V/H	N/T	S/A	Q	N	G/S	N	R	Q	L	K	D	XXXXX E X X E E Y
Tub1C1	R	T	C	E	K	S	T	S	R/K	Q/A	A/S	N	X D X X E E X E N G E Y